

MOVING D4.3 Excel Template Conversion Guidance Notes

Introduction

The following brief notes are intended to assist users in the completion of the MOVING – D4.3 Template Conversion – June 2022 excel workbook.

This has been developed from the D4.3 Annex – Template for DT review v4.0_excel development word document.

Contents

Contents and Metadata

This tab lists the contents of the workbook and some of the key metadata.

Updates

Intended to capture updates in the development of the workbook – since this is being developed in OneDrive updates are continually applied/saved which renders version control largely redundant.

Input Data Sheet Section 2, 3, 4, 5, 6

These tabs from the bulk of the workbook and are numbered according to the same sections of the word document. A separate data sheet exists for each numbered section (2-6).

Control Ranges

These serve the dropdown lists encountered in the Input Data Sheets. It should never need intervention and may be relegated to a ‘hidden’ sheet.

Reference

A reference list for the 23 case studies.

Design Notes

Style

The style of headings, sections, etc present in the Excel reflect the same sections in the Word document.

Development

- Row 4 is a “dummy row” and is the row used to design and build what is required. This row is then copied into the 23 case study rows.
- Where possible a **bold green outline** has been applied to groups of cells reflecting entries from the same table in the word document. This is to help the user in data entry.
- Gaps have been added between tables using a stippled column , again to assist the user.
- Conditional formatting has been applied to the sheets to colour cells depending on their contents. This currently includes:

- “Not for excel” cells should be grey. This indicate questions in the word template which are not encoded in, or not intended for, excel.
- “Free text” – any cell containing free text will be coloured in . There are no data validation restrictions on these cells so anything goes. This beige formatting will be removed when the cell is overwritten.
- Each cell, when selected, brings up a dialog box showing what is expected to be entered in that cell. If relevant, this also includes the question that is asked in the word document. Usually either “Free text” or “Select from dropdown” is included. Examples are given below:

- In the event of a dropdown the grey down arrow should be clicked which will show the available options for the cell. These are predetermined and set by the various lists in the Control Ranges tab. If the data to be entered is not present, it is recommended that either a note be added to the cell or that the “Queries” document is updated and Dave will address.
- Remember the contents of the cell as they exist at the start are expected to be overwritten.

Completion of workbook

General

The design of the workbook allows two types of data entry – dropdown list, or free text.

Dropdown

The simplest case is where a dropdown menu exists. Simply select one of the options presented. If no data exists in the word document then select the “NoData” option. If you think an additional option should be added to the list that isn’t already, please mark the cell with a note.

Free Text

Free text allows the user to enter anything into the cell. However some rules of thumb should be used as follows:

- If entering a list of values in a cell, use a semi-colon “;” to separate entities.
 - E.g.
 - “Spring water for mash; Distillery local knowledge” or

- “Images; landscape; history”
- “self catering; catered provision; guest houses, hotels” – for this one “guest houses, hotels” would be treated as a separate entity.
- In the event that the cell is not populated, enter “N/A” or “NoData”

Updates

If you need anything added to the dropdown lists it’s best to use the “Queries on excel work – for Dave” or the Webex chat.

Guidance to change data validation rules....

During the meeting of 18th July Kirsty asked for guidance in the event that the data validation rules had to be altered/removed. Some descriptive notes are provided below....

There’s a bit to this – and if you’re unsure, **just ask Dave!**

Data Validation Rules – Adding a new option

First – select the cell from the dummy row in the workbook for which you wish the data validation to be changed.

Then go to the **Data** menu option... and find the **Data Validation** button in the Data Tools group.

Select **Data Validation** from the dropdown list. This will show the Data Validation dialog box

The Settings tab here gives you access to the criteria.

In this case the permissible values are controlled by a list – A2-A6 from the Control Ranges tab.

The **Control Ranges** tab contains the data needed for the various dropdown lists to operate throughout the workbook. If these need to be added to then there's a knack to this...

First **Cancel** the Data Validation dialog.

Go to the **Control Ranges** tab

The knack is this... If you insert a new cell into the list above the last entry (i.e. above NoData which should be the last option in all lists) then any data validation referencing those cells will 'pick up' the extra cell.

For example say you want to edit the Commodity list and include "Unsure".

Commodity
Premium
Commodity
Discount
Other
NoData

You'd right click on "NoData" (the last value in list), select 'Insert' from the options and choose the 'Shift cells down' option.

That will create an extra empty cell above NoData into which you can add the extra category..

Commodity	Commodity
Premium	Premium
Commodity	Commodity
Discount	Discount
Other	Other
	Unsure
NoData	NoData

Doing it this way will mean that **any** dropdowns which reference this list will recognise the list has expanded and add the new category to the dropdown.